

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Benzoic Acids in Methanol and Water Mixtures by Conductometric Methods

A. K. MANDAL and S. C. LAHIRI

Department of Chemistry, Kalyani University, West Bengal, India.

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The pK_a values of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acids in methanol-water mixtures (8-75.9 wt. % of methanol) were determined using modified conductometric method suggested by Gelb with slight change. The results have been further verified by Fuoss-Kraus method. The limitations of the present state of knowledge of solution chemistry in accounting the variations of the dissociation constants with solvent composition have been stressed.

THE determination of ionization equilibria in mixed solvents has received considerable attention. The potentiometric method utilizing the hydrogen electrode as reference electrode is difficult and can be applied only in absence of complicating reduction reactions. The method also suffers from the inherent limitation that the e.m.f. of standard hydrogen electrode is taken to be zero in all the solvent systems and at all temperatures. This, however, as rightly pointed out by Popovych¹, generates quite a large number of thermodynamically unrelated pH or e.m.f. scales as there are solvents making the correlation of pK values in different solvents difficult.

Recently, Panichajakul and Woolley² suggested a rapid and convenient method for determination of weak acids in aquo-organic mixed solvents using glass-electrodes assuming that the glass electrode junction potentials, asymmetry potentials and responses do not change with solvent composition and the electrolytes are completely dissociated in the mixed solvents.

In search of a suitable method which could give ionization constants avoiding difficulty and assumptions, we found that the conductometric method as suggested by Gelb³ can be utilized with success in mixed solvents with little modification. In this paper, we report the dissociation constants of benzoic, *m*-fluoro, *m*-chloro and *p*-bromo benzoic acids in methanol water mixtures. The results have been further verified by Fuoss-Kraus method^{4,5}.

Experimental

Methanol (E. Merck) was purified and the weight percentages of methanol in alcohol-water mixtures and their relative permittivities were determined in the same way as described before^{6,7}. Benzoic acid (G. R., E. Merck), *m*-chloro-benzoic acid (Puriss, Fluka),

m-fluoro-benzoic acid (Purum, Fluka) and *p*-bromo benzoic acid (Purum, Fluka) were all crystallised from alcohol. The purity of the samples was tested by melting-point determination. The organic acids and perchloric acid (G. R., E. Merck) were estimated volumetrically in the usual way. Caustic soda, succinic acid and potassium hydrogen phthalate were of E. Merck's G. R. grade. Conductivity water was obtained by redistilling the distilled water with alkaline permanganate from all glass distilling set. Care has been taken to avoid contamination of water and solvents with CO_2 .

The conductometric 'titration' of benzoic acid with $HClO_4$ and the blank 'titration' were performed in the same way as described before³. The ionic strengths of the solutions were kept as low as practicable ($\approx 10^{-4}M$ to $10^{-3}M$). The experiment was repeated several times with different concentrations of benzoic acid (ranging from 1×10^{-4} to $1 \times 10^{-3}M$). Similar measurements were made in different percentages of methanol-water mixtures (0 to 75.9% by wt. of methanol) and with *m*-chloro-, *m*-fluoro- and *p*-bromo-benzoic acids.

For the determination of dissociation constants by Fuoss-Kraus method, the conductances of the different concentrations of these acids (Concentration range $10^{-4}M$ to $10^{-3}M$) were measured several times making appropriate corrections for the conductances of the solvents.

Conductance measurements were made with the aid of a Leeds and Northrup Model 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of 0.1%. A 50-60 cycle signal was employed. A dip-type conductance cell (cell constant = 0.85 cm^{-1}) was used. The measurements were performed at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$.

Results

For a mixture of completely dissociated HClO₄ and partly dissociated HA, the dissociation constant for the reaction

can be written as

$$K = \frac{\alpha(C_{HA} + C_{HClO_4}) \times f^{\pm} \pm}{(1 - \alpha)}$$

the terms have their usual significance. However, when the conductances of the mixture (1/R) (containing HA and HClO₄) and blank solutions (1/R*) (containing HClO₄ only) are equal, we have (following Gelb⁸)

$$C_{HClO_4} \cdot \Lambda'_{HClO_4} + \alpha C_{HA} \cdot \Lambda'_{HA} = C^*_{HClO_4} \cdot \Lambda'^*_{HClO_4}$$

and $C_{HClO_4} + \alpha C_{HA} = C^*_{HClO_4}$

assuming $\Lambda'_{HClO_4} = \Lambda'_{HA}$ and $\Lambda'^*_{HClO_4} = \Lambda'^*_{HClO_4}$

in aqueous and mixed solvents from which α can be calculated. Λ' = Equivalent conductance of the completely dissociated electrolyte at any ionic strength and Λ = The equivalent conductance of the electrolyte at that ionic strength i.e. $\Lambda = \alpha \Lambda'$

($\alpha=1$, in case of HClO₄ and * indicates the quantities in blank solutions).

We have kept ionic strength sufficiently low and the variations of ionic strengths are too small to vitiate the Λ values appreciably. However, refinements of K values are possible taking

$$\alpha = (C^*_{HClO_4} - C_{HClO_4}) / \beta C_{HA}$$

where $\beta = \frac{\Lambda'_{HA}}{\Lambda'_{HClO_4}}$

The procedure as suggested by Gelb to calculate β is rather cumbersome. We, therefore, adopted an alternative procedure to calculate β values. The Λ° values of HA and HClO₄ in mixed solvents were determined as given below. The ratio $\Lambda^\circ_{HA} / \Lambda^\circ_{HClO_4}$ gives β directly since the ionic strength and the concentrations of HA and HClO₄ are low. β -values are likely to be of the same order of magnitude in water as well as in different mixed solvents, as the variations of mobility of anions in different solvents are likely to follow the similar pattern. The results are given in table 1.

The dissociation constant values have also been checked in the following way.

Λ° values of perchloric acids in different mixed-solvents have been determined in the same way as

described before⁸. The initial values of Λ°_{HA} and K of weak acids in mixed solvents were determined from the plot of ΛC against $1/\Lambda$ of a number of dilute solutions of HA utilizing the equation

$$\Lambda C = -K \Lambda^\circ + K \Lambda^\circ{}^2 / \Lambda$$

(Λ° = Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution). The improvement in the values of Λ°_{HA} and K were made using the method of Fuoss and Kraus^{4,5}. The plots of $F(Z)/\Lambda$ against $\Lambda C f^{\pm}_\pm / F(Z)$ showed good straight lines wherefrom K and Λ° values were calculated utilizing the equation

$$F(Z)/\Lambda = \frac{1}{K \Lambda^\circ{}^2} \frac{\Lambda C f^{\pm}_\pm}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^\circ}$$

The values of the constants in the Onsager equation were calculated from the interpolated values of viscosities and dielectric constants of methanol-water mixtures from the data given by Bates and Robinson⁹ and $F(Z)$ values were calculated from the computed values of $F(Z)$ using Λ° values previously determined.

The log f^\pm values were calculated from the equation

$$-\log f^\pm = A \sqrt{\alpha C}$$

using the appropriate values of A.

Discussions

The average values of Λ° and pK of different organic acids in aquo-organic mixtures are given in the table 1. Considering the limitations, the results obtained from titration method and Fuoss-Kraus method agree fairly well. The accuracy of the extrapolated Λ° values is known to be rather low. In spite of the limitations, the Λ° values as given in table 1 seem to be quite in order. Λ° values decrease as the percentage of organic solvent increases as noted by Shedlovsky¹⁰ et al. It is also observed that Λ° values are higher in methanol-water mixtures compared to those in ethanol-water mixtures as expected. The pK values of benzoic acid in methanol-water mixtures have been reported by Bacarella et al¹¹. Our results show that the agreement is excellent upto 54.20% or even upto 75.94% by wt. of methanol considering the limits of accuracy (± 0.04 in water to ± 0.10 in higher percentages of mixed solvent). However, the values determined by pH-titration or potentiometric method seem to be a bit high compared to conductometric method in aquo-organic mixtures as evinced from the pK_a' values of acetic acid in methanol-water mixtures determined potentiometrically and conductometrically¹⁰.

The results show a good linearity when pK is plotted against mole-fractions of organic solvent or $1/\epsilon$ upto about 65 wt % of organic solvents. Deviations are apparent at high percentages. Marginal improvement occurs when the activities of water are taken into consideration as suggested by Yasuda¹².

TABLE I

Wt.% of MeOH	Mole fraction of MeOH	(1/ε) ×100	Λ° mhos Cm ² /equiv			pKa of benzoic		pKa of <i>m</i> -F.B.A.		pKa of <i>m</i> -C.B.A.		pKa of <i>p</i> -B.B.A.							
			HClO ₄	B. A.	F.B.A.	C.B.A.	B.B.A.	(a)	(a')	(b)	(a)	(a')	(b)	(a)	(a')	(b)			
8.0	0.0000	1.27	415.0	392.5	390.6	391.8	386.0	4.17	4.20	4.21	3.84	3.87	8.86	3.81	3.84	3.85	3.94	3.94	3.98
8.0	0.0470	1.33	381.0	360.0	365.0	358.0	355.7	4.30	4.32	4.31	3.94	3.98	3.98	3.92	3.95	3.98	4.12	4.15	4.16
16.0	0.0968	1.40	331.3	308.0	312.0	307.0	302.9	4.45	4.50	4.51	4.10	4.18	4.22	4.12	4.20	4.23	4.25	4.30	4.34
25.2	0.1593	1.48	280.5	263.1	263.0	259.0	260.0	4.66	4.75	4.75	4.32	4.42	4.45	4.25	4.34	4.38	4.40	4.49	4.53
34.4	0.2279	1.57	228.0	218.0	214.0	216.0	212.7	4.88	4.98	5.01	4.56	4.66	4.64	4.54	4.59	4.62	4.68	4.75	4.71
44.7	0.3126	1.69	195.1	182.0	180.0	185.0	178.0	5.14	5.21	5.25	4.73	4.80	4.83	4.70	4.80	4.82	4.85	4.96	4.95
54.2	0.3997	1.84	171.7	157.0	148.0	152.0	155.0	5.39	5.50	5.53	5.00	5.10	5.12	5.00	5.05	5.09	5.11	5.21	5.24
64.1	0.5000	2.01	151.5	137.5	139.0	135.7	140.0	5.64	5.76	5.76	5.25	5.36	5.35	5.20	5.30	5.35	5.40	8.52	5.54
75.9	0.6392	2.25	131.0	118.0	115.0	119.5	121.0	5.92	6.02	6.07	5.56	5.68	5.71	5.5	5.60	5.62	5.57	5.72	5.75

B.A. = Benzoic acid, F.B.A. = *m*-fluoro benzoic acid, C.B.A. = *m*-chloro benzoic acid, B.B.A. = *p*-bromo benzoic acid.

a) average pKa values from plotting of ΛC vs. (1/Λ ; a') average pKa values from Fuoss-Kraus method.

b) average pKa values from 'titration' method.

The approximate difference of pK -values in mixed solvents can be had from Born¹³ equation

$$\Delta pK = pK(s) - pK(w) = 121.6 (1/\epsilon - 0.0128) (1/r_A + 1/r_H)$$

(r_A and r_H represent the radii of the acid anion and proton respectively). However, ΔpK values calculated with $r_H = 0.86 \text{ \AA}$ ¹⁴ and $r_A = 0.55 \text{ \AA}$ ⁹ do not agree with the experimental values. This may be due to (i) uncertain values of radii, (ii) approximate nature of the equation. Furthermore, (iii) solute-solvent interactions and solvent-basicity have not been taken into consideration. Modifications of the Born equation which take into account of the local variations in dielectric constant within the solvation shells make some improvement¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The theory of Hiromi⁸ which takes into account the particular geometry and charge distribution within organic ion is also inadequate as it predicts the variation of pK against $1/\epsilon$.

The difference between $[pK(s) - pK(w)]_R$ and $[pK(s) - pK(w)]_O$ [where R=substituted acid and O=unsubstituted acid] should be linearly related to $1/\epsilon$ as expected from the equation but actually not observed in practice

$$\begin{aligned} [pK(s) - pK(w)]_R - [pK(s) - pK(w)]_O \\ = 121.6 (1/\epsilon - 0.0128) (1/r_{AR} - 1/r_{AO}) \end{aligned}$$

The equation cancels the term due to free-energy of transfer of H^+ ions and therefore, is likely to be obeyed as the observed deviations have generally been assumed to be due to the free-energy of transfer of proton from water to different alcohol mixtures which is not a linear function of $1/\epsilon$ ¹⁹.

It is imperative that the proper knowledge of the "non-electrostatic" contributions resulting from the interactions between the solute species with solvent molecules is necessary to understand the behaviour of solvents. It is natural that structural modifications and ionic solvation and complications arising from the equilibria of the type

has pronounced effect. Furthermore, the free-energy of transfer of proton from water to methanol + water mixtures upto 50% w/w methanol has been regarded to be due to the transfer of a tetrahedral-aquo proton from water into the mixture and subsequent replacement of an H_2O molecule by CH_3OH molecule²⁰.

Further replacement of water molecule by CH_3OH molecule is possible but we have no definite knowledge of the various interactions and displacement process. The question of anion solvation is intriguing and evading.

The ΔpK_a values of all these acids are the same within limits of experimental accuracy. Since the acids are of the same charge types with the same ionizing group having almost the same size, an approximate equality of "medium effect" is expected. A little variation, however, may be explained as due to the preferential solvation of uncharged acids by methanol molecules and ions by water molecules. It is expected that the ratios of water molecules in the solvation shells of uncharged acids and particularly of anions are changed considerably by the presence of the strongly polar substituent in the benzene ring. Polar substituents will have a natural tendency to increase the water molecules in the solvation shells of anions compared to uncharged acids leading to a favourable free-energy change. The structural modifications and ionic solutions will also have profound effect.

In fine, we stress the need of determining the dissociation constants of weak acids in mixed solvent by conductometric methods with better bridges and find out the reliabilities of different methods. These may prove useful to find out unambiguous method of determining the dissociation constants in mixed solvents free from assumptions.

References

- O. POPOVYCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1974, 49, 2009.
- C. C. PANICHAJAKUL and E. M. WOOLLEY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1975, 47, 1860.
- R. I. GELB, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 1110.
- R. M. FUOSS and C. KRAUS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 476, 2390.
- R. M. FUOSS and F. ACCASCINA, *Electrolytic Conductance*. Interscience Publication Inc., New York, 1959.
- D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1975, 79, 335.
- G. BISWAS, S. ADITYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1977, 19, 55.
- A. K. MANDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1976, 49, 1829.
- R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON, *Chemical Physics of Ionic Solutions*, Eds. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARADAS, J. WILEY AND SONS, INC. New York, 1966.
- T. SHEDLOVSKY and R. L. KAY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 151.
- A. L. BACARELLA, E. GRUNWALD, H. MARSHALL and E. L. PURLEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 757.
- M. YASUDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1959, 32, 429.
- M. BORN, *Z. Physik.*, 1920, 1, 45.
- E. E. SAGER, R. A. ROBINSON and R. C. BATES, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1965, A69, 62.
- M. PAABO, R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 247.
- L. G. HEPLER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, 17, 587.
- R. H. STOKES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 979.
- K. HIROMI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1960, 33, 1251.
- G. H. PARSONS and C. H. ROCHESTER, *J.C.S. Faraday I*, 1975, 71, 1058.
- C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc. Farad. I*, 1973, 69, 984.